

MARKETING EFFICIENCY OF *Garcinia cola* (Bitter cola) AND *Afomomum melegneta* (Alligator pepper) in IBADAN METROPOLIS, OYO STATE.

Famuyide, O.O., Adebayo, O., Bolaji-Olutunji, K.A and Oladeji, O.
Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, P.M.B 5054, Ibadan
(tunjikofoworola@yahoo.com)

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the marketing efficiency as well as the profitability of *Garcinia cola* and *Afomomum melegneta* in selected markets in Ibadan, Oyo State. A total of eighty sellers are interviewed with structured questionnaire and oral interview. The selected markets are Oja'ba, Agbeni, Bode, Shasha and Ojo. Simple descriptive analyses such as percentage and frequency table were used to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents while gross margin and regression analyses were employed to determine the profitability and efficiency of the markets. The result shows that 88% of the sellers are women while 22% were men. 88% of respondents were involved in selling *G.col*a and *A.melegneta*, 5% accounted for *A.melegneta* alone, while remaining 7% is for *G.col*a, *A.melegneta* and *kola nut*. 85% of the sellers were 40 years and above and had between 10 and 50 years of experience. This was due to the fact that these people inherited the business from the parents or formally learn the business. Two functional regression forms were used, Weighted Least Square and Linear Regression Analyses. The best fit for *Garcinia cola* is Weighted Least Square with Coefficient of Multiple determination, R^2 , of 0.556 and coefficient of multiple correlation of 0.75. Linear regression analysis gave the best fit for *A.melegneta* with coefficient of multiple determination, R^2 of 0.78 and coefficient of multiple correlation of 0.88. The R^2 was used to explain the degree of variability in the dependent variable (Y) from the view point independent variables (X_1 ----- X_6) while R evaluate the degree of association between Y and X. The Marketing Efficiency (ME) are 1.69 and 1.29 for *G.col*a and *A.melegneta* respectively. This implies that for every naira (N1) spent on *G.col*a there is 69k return and a return of 28k on every naira spent on *A.melegneta*. Marketing of *G.col*a and *A.melegneta* can be said to be profitable, efficient and sustainable. The business can alleviate poverty. Therefore, further research should be carried out to grow these products more around South West Nigeria to make it more abundant and to reduce procurement.

KEYWORDS: Efficiency, marketing, Non timber, marketing, *garcinia cola*, *afomomum melegneta*, poverty.

INTRODUCTION

Forests provide important sources of income to many people in West Africa forest zones. Forest products are traded in both local and urban markets, and are sold to meet both rural and urban consumer needs. A great number of forest foods are gathered and sold in the local markets of the region including semi wild produce from trees on farm and fallow lands. There are timber (woody) and non timber forest products (Andel, 2006). Andel (2006) further observed that, millions of people especially those living in rural areas in developing countries including Nigeria collect these products daily and many, regard selling these products as a means of earning a living. The use of non timber forest products is as old as human existence. In subsistence and rural economic, the role and contribution of non-timber forest product (NTFPs) in the daily life and welfare of people all over the world are crucial because of the richness of their variety, as insects, animals fodder, fiber, fertilizer, medicinal extracts, construction materials, cosmetic and cultural products and natural dyes, tannin, gums, resins, latex and other exudates, essential oils, spices edible oils, decorative articles, horns, tusks, bones, pelts, plumes, hides and skins, non-ligno- cellulosic products, phyto-chemicals and aroma chemicals. These products are derived from a variety of sources plants (palms, grasses, herbs, shrubs trees, and animals (insect, birds, reptile, large animals) and other non-living component of the ecosystem. Different parts of a plant or animal often provide different products simultaneously and or at different times.

About 80% of the population of the developing world depends on NTFPs for their primary health and nutritional needs (FAO, 1995). It is therefore paradoxical that in spite of their real and potential values, most of NTFPs

remain grouped as minor products of forest. These products rarely feature in statistics and are hardly studied or researched until recently. Several NTFPs are in existence that are of economic, nutritional and medicinal importance. NTFPs are grossly affected by seasonal changes and this in turn affects their availability and prices. *Garcinia cola* and *Afomomum melegneta* are one of the major NTFPs in West Africa.

Garcinia Cola

Garcinia cola known as bitter cola is a medicinal plant which is exclusively tropical in distribution. Traditionally Africa medicine regards the plant in high esteem (Gill, 1978). It is cultivated throughout West Africa for its edible fruits and seed which are used as a rejuvenating agent for masticatory purposes and as a general antidote (Ibibilo, 1983). This medium size tree is easily recognized by its hairy flower and large fruits which have the size and colour of an orange. It flowers between December and January with fine reddish hairs on the outside of the sepals and petals; fruits around July and October, about 6cm in diameter, orange colour pulp and the seed are edible, wood yellowish darkening to brown at the center, hard, close-grained. The trees are found in humid lowland forest area of Nigeria, Cameroun, Ghana and Benin republic and there are different species of *G. kola*. These are different in fruit colours, aromatic strength and sizes. (Field Survey, 2010). The different varieties of nut give a greater or lesser percentage of caffeine which is only found in fresh state. The seeds are said to contain glucoside and kolanin. They also contain starch, sugar and fat decomposing enzyme acting which on various oils. It is a nervine and heart tonic. (Bitter cola cooperative, 2008).

Many pharmacological effects have been demonstrated for the bioflavonoid in *G. kola* extractives. Along the antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti diabetics and bronchodilator properties (Iwu, 1993, Okoro 1993). Some proprietary dietary supplement containing *G. kola* extractive already exist in the USA and Africa markets (Okoro 1993). The exploration of *G. kola*, alongside with other antimicrobials in the fight against deadly human diseases like HIV and AIDS is presently on (Iwu *et al* 1999). Experiments using *G. kola* kernel as hop substitutes in several indigenous alcoholic drinks as well as a flavor enhancer in the beverage industry also exist (FDA, 1999). Ofor *et al* (2004) identified several ethno-botanical uses to which the indigenes of Imo state, Southeastern Nigeria, put the *G. kola* seeds. These include as an antidote to snake bite, poison, overdose and used as snake repellents. The branch stick is also used as chewing stick to clear or clean the mouth and improve mouth odour. The seed are eaten ordinarily to cure cough, nasal congestion, vomiting, hepatics, and to alleviate hypertension.

Afomomum melegneta

Afomomum melegneta commonly known as Alligator pepper is one of the non timber forest products species from the sub humid tropical environment. These are canna-like plant except that leafy stems and flowering stems are quite separate both, arising from a creeping rhizome. *A. melegneta* is often cultivated in most lowland forest regions but it also grows in the forest. The plant is about 1m high with bamboo-like leaves in two rows. Single, usually white to pink flowers are produced on separate stalks at the base of the plant. The fruit are smooth, dark red and grooved. *A. melegneta* is the source of aromatic seed known as grains of paradise which are widely used for medicinal and other economic values. The crop is seldom deliberately cultivated in Nigeria. The alligator pepper is popularly used as spice and mainly as food and brewing. It is used traditionally as medicine to treat constipation, hemorrhoids, worm infestation as well as in pronouncing blessing on people. When a baby is born in Yoruba culture, they are given a small taste after birth as part of the routine baby welcoming process. In Igbo land, alligator pepper with kola nut is used in naming ceremony, as presentation to visiting guest and for other social events. It is a painless and safe medication for men suffering from erectile dysfunction and premature ejaculation as well as to improve sexual performance. (Oguntola, 2010).

Marketing Concept

Marketing involves making contact between buyers and sellers for purpose of selling and buying according to Eyiye (1991). Kotler (1995), stated that marketing is a matter of getting the right goods and services in the right place at the right time with the right communication promotion. Bamigboye (1995), described marketing as a management process that is responsible for the identification, anticipation and satisfaction of consumer requirement. Marketing is the sum total activities involved in a market. Some markets, for example, shops and stall, physically bring together the sellers and buyers. The essential features of markets are demand, the behavior of buyers, supply and behavior of sellers. The unique role of marketing is, therefore the act that link production and consumption point. Marketing plays a vital role in the process because a well organized efficient market structure ensures profitable return to sellers at reasonable low prices to consumers, The efficiency of marketing influences how producers will increase their output as said by Usman *et al*, 2010.

Objective

1. To determine the socioeconomic importance of *G. kola* and *A.melegneta* in Ibadan metropolis and the effects on profitability.
2. To determine the profitability of the *Garcinia cola* and *A. melegneta* marketing.
3. To determine the marketing efficiency of the two NTFPs

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was carried out in Ibadan metropolis. Ibadan is the capital of Oyo State, the biggest City in Nigeria and sub-Sahara Africa. It has population of 2,550,593 (Nigeria population Census, 2006). The city is located on the Southern Western part of Nigeria, lying between latitude 7⁰ and 9⁰N of the equator, longitude 3⁰E and 5⁰E Greenwich meridian. It has an average rainfall of between 1250 mm and 1800mm. The temperature range is between 27⁰C and 32⁰C with relative humidity of about 75% to 90%. Ibadan metropolis consists of five local Government areas, namely Ibadan North, Southeast, North-West South-East and South West respectively. The indigenous language is Yoruba and major commercial activities are concentrated in the urban center of the state. There are little farming activities in the city hence most of the food consumed in the city, are produced outside the city especially in the surrounding villages.

Data collection

The data were collected through the use of structured questionnaire and oral interview. Six major markets, Oja’ba, Agbeni, Bode, Dugbe, Shasha, and Ojo markets were purposively selected after the reconnaissance survey and eighty copies of the questionnaires were administered in all. The questionnaires were not uniformly administered because the sellers vary in their concentration in different markets. Forty-two questionnaires were administered in Oja’ba having the highest population of the wholesalers, a major market in Ibadan and the headquarter of all the sellers not only in Ibadan, but Oyo State; Sixteen in Agbeni market; two in Bode market; ten in Dugbe market; six in Shasha market and four in Ojoo market.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such percentage frequency table, and regression analytical methods were employed for the analysis of the data of the study.

The following models as used by Okumadewa *et al* (2000) were adopted for the analysis.

$$\text{Gross margin} = \text{Total Revenue} - \text{Cost Price}$$

$$\text{Marketing Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Total revenue}}{\text{Total Marketing Cost}}$$

The following implicit model was used to represent the determinants of profitability of the markets.

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n) \text{ i.e.}$$

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5$$

Where,

Y = profitability

b₀ = profit constant

b₁-----b₅ = coefficient of independent variables

X₁-X₅ = specific independent variables

X₁ = Age

X₂ = Marital status

X₃ = Educational level

X₄ = Non timber forest product selling

X₅ = Experience in years

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomics Characteristics of the marketers

From Table 1 95% of the sellers were women and sellers of *G. cola* and *A. melegneta* respectively. 48% did not have formal education at all while the remaining 52% had up to secondary education. 15% of the marketers were of age between 20-29 while 80% were 30 years and above and 75% had more than twenty years of experience. This shows that most of the marketers in the business were older women; who were probably born into and remain in the business they were born into the business and continue even in their old ages. 72% were married, while 25% were widows. Most of the marketers (63%) got their supply from village markets within and outside the state like Ogunmakin in Oyo state, Mamu in Ogun; Gbongan, Ikire and Total in Osun state; Ayede Ogbese and Owena in Ondo state and Ayetoro, and Iye markets in Ekiti State, even some high quality *A. melegneta* were obtained from Ghana. The remaining 37% got theirs from Oja'ba market which has 53% of the sellers in Ibadan. It is also the headquarter of the sellers association in Ibadan even Oyo state. The sellers are controlled and given information about price, safety, where and when to market. The association also protect the sellers all over the state. The members pay between N700-N1,000 to the association and collect receipt or tickets so no need to pay at all as an individual to the local or state government again, it is been settled by the association.

Table 1. Socio-economic Characteristics of *G. cola* and *A. melegneta*

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	10	12.5
Female	70	87.5
Total	80	100
Age		
20-29	12	15
30-39	2	30
40-49	14	17.5
50-60	20	25
60+	10	12.5
Total	80	100
Marital status		
Single	8	10
Married	50	62.5
Widow	20	25
Divorce	2	2.5
Total	80	100
Educational Qualification		
None	38	47.5
Primary	28	35
Secondary	14	17.5
Tertiary	0	0
Total	80	100
Year of Experience		
10-20	20	25
21-30	18	22.5
31-40	10	12.5
40-50	32	41
Total	80	100
Sources		
Urban markets	30	37.5
Rural markets	50	62.5
Total	80	100

Table 2.Selling price per unit

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Price per unit <i>G.cola</i> (basket)		
N7,000-N8,000	60	75
>N8,000-N9,000	20	25
Total	80	100
Price per Total unit of <i>A. melegneta</i> (50s)		
N250 –N400	58	72.5s
>N400-N600	22	27.5
Total	80	100

Regression Analysis

Two regression functions were used; these were Linear regression model and Weighted least square analysis. The Weighted Least Square provided the function with the best fit for *G. cola*. The obtained function is

$$Y_G = 5297.892 + 489.193X_1 - 216.400X_2 + 403.301X_3 - 885.085X_4 + 76.934X_5$$

(2750) (293.942) * (776.365) (572.200) (270.272.) (45.300)*

* ---significant at 5%

The explanations of the statistics of this function are provided in Table 3. The weighted least square model has the best fit for *G.cola* with the regression Coefficient of 0.566 i.e 56% of the predictors explain the dependent variables. The marital status and different NTFPs sold by the sellers have negative relationships with the profit made on *G.cola* while the age, the years of experience and educational qualification, have positive relationships at 0.05 level of significant with the profit made, that is the more the years of experience and age the more the profit made in *G.cola* trading.

Table 4. shows that the best fit equation for *A.melegneta* is Linear regression with regression coefficient of 0.781 i.e78% for the predictors, age ,marital status, Years of experience, different NTFPs ,educational status, gender explain the dependent variable profit. The equation obtained is

$$Y_A = 4354.300 + 688.317X_1 + 178.591X_2 - 63.550X_3 + 433.610X_4 + 86.634X_5$$

(1169.835) (248.452) * (339.675) (250.104) (994.459) (25.7230)*

*-----Significant at 5%

The statistics of the function are provided in Table 4.But the marital status, years of experience and age have positive relationship and were significant at 0.05, level of significant. Therefore the more the age and years of experience the higher the profit made on *A.melegneta*.

Table 5 Shows the budgetary analysis of *G.cola* and *A.melegneta*. The marketing are profitable because the Gross profit has positive difference of 7,990.1 (33474.5 – 25484.375) for *G.cola* and Gross margin of 7,250 (57,250 – 30,000) for *A. melegneta*. This is in agreement with Usman *et al* (2007) in a work on Analysis of NTFP, *Thaumatococcus danielli* which also gave positive difference between average revenue and cost price. The Marketing Efficiency is above one (1) that is,1.689 for *G.cola* and 1.28 for *A.melegneta*.This implies that the market is very efficient , excess profit, well organized, coordinated and sustainable. In other words for every one naira(N1) spent on *G.cola*, there is a return of 69k and a return of 28k for every one naira (N1) spent on *A. melegneta*. According to Usman *et al.* (2010), if marketing efficiency (ME), it shows that the market is efficient, if is greater than one (1) there is excess profit and if less than one (1) there is inefficiency.

It was also discovered from the field, that the members pay annual fee of N700- N1, 000 to the association and collect ticket, without which no seller will be allowed to operate in the market. This as observed is a very strong caucus and not easily penetrated. There are few sellers, few buyers, having control over the market and the price. This implies an Oligopolistic Market Structure.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The marketing of *G. cola* and *A. melegneta* are very efficient, profitable and sustainable as discovered from the empirical research study. It is a market involved by few sellers and few buyers i.e Oligopolistic markets. The business can therefore alleviate poverty even with little capital. Research should be carried out to grow these products more around South west Nigeria to reduce the sellers' travelling long distance to purchase the products.

Table 3. Regression Analysis For *Garcinia. cola* (Weighted Least Square Analysis)

Variable	Coefficient B	Standard Error	T value	Sig	R ²	R
Constant	5297.982	2750.954	1.926	.065		
Age	483.193	293.942	1.644	.112	.556	.753
Maritals	-216.400	776.365	-.279	.783		
Edu- Qua	403.301	572.200	.705	.487		
NTFPs	-855.085	270.272	-3.062	.005		
Exp. Yrs	76.934	45.300	1.695	.102		

Source: Field Survey, 2010

Table 4. Regression Analysis For *Afomomum melegneta* (Linear Regression Analysis)

Variables	Coefficient B	Standard Error	T value	Sig	R ²	R
Constant	4354.300	1169.835	3.722	.003		
Age	688.317	248.452	-2.770	.017	.781	.884
Marital st.	178.591	339.675	.520	.613		
Edu-Qual	-63.550	250.104	-.254	.804		
NTFPs	433.610	94.459	-4.590	.001		
Exp. Yrs	86.634	25.723	3.368	.006		

Source: Field Survey, 2010.

Table 5. Budgetary Analysis

Product	Av. Revenue	Av. Cost	Gross Margin
<i>Garcinia cola</i>	N33,474.50	N25,484.38	N7,990.1
<i>Afomomum melegneta</i>	N57,250	N30,000	N7,250

Source : Field Survey, 2010

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Corresponding author

Famuyide, O.O. ,

Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, P.M.B 5054, Ibadan

Email; tunjikofoworola@yahoo.com